

OPERATIONS RESEARCH IN CIVIL ENGINEERING AND GEODESY ACADEMIC STUDIES IN FORMER YUGOSLAV REPUBLICS

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Abstract: *The research presented in this paper is an extended research on the implementation of operations research in the subjects of undergraduate (bachelor) and master academic studies at the faculties of civil engineering and geodesy. For the purposes of this research, besides the Republic of Serbia, five more countries in the region were included: Bosnia and Herzegovina, Croatia, Slovenia, Montenegro, and the Republic of North Macedonia. A total of fourteen faculties from former Yugoslav countries were analyzed, and all of them are public, except UNION Nikola Tesla. This topic emphasizes the importance of implementing operations research in civil engineering and geodesy subjects as a mathematical method of decision-making.*

Keywords: *Operations research, civil engineering, geodesy, bachelor programmes, master studies.*

1. INTRODUCTION

Operations research is a field of applied mathematics that integrates advanced analytics methods to improve management and decision-making (Medium, 2021). Moreover, mathematical tools are used not only to investigate mathematics further, but rather to build mathematical models, analyze complex situations, and solve problems within the operations research domains (Stonybrook, 2025). Its historical origins are in the 17th century (Medium, 2021) when mathematicians Blaise Pascal and Christiaan Huygens solved problems involving complex decisions (the problem of points - a classical problem in probability theory) by using game-theoretic ideas and expected values, while Pierre de Fermat and Jacob Bernoulli solved these types of problems using combinatorial reasoning instead. The modern version of operations research dates back to World War II, when scientists and mathematicians were recruited to solve complex military problems such as critical logistics and supply chain issues. In 1938, the term operations research was used for the first time by a group of British Royal Air Force officers and civilian scientists who were asked to determine how recently developed radar technology could be integrated into the wider air defence network (Assad, 2011). In 1947, an American mathematician George B. Dantzig created the first mathematical technique of operations research, called the Simplex Method, which greatly simplified the solution of linear programming problems (University, 2025). According to C. Goodeve (Goodeve, 1948) the operations research represents a scientific method for providing executive departments with a quantitative basis for decisions regarding the operations under their control. The purpose of operations research is to translate complicated, but important real-world problems into precise, quantitative language that can be clearly and unambiguously analysed (Rajgopal, 2025). According to (Gupta, 2019), the operations research development stages consist of the following six sequential steps: (i) Observation of the problematic setting and the problem formulation; (ii) Creating a model; (iii) Deriving the solution from the model; (iv) Testing the model and its solution as well as updating the model; (v) Establishing control over the solution, and (vi) Implementation of the final results. In order to optimize and improve decision-making processes different techniques can be used (Kapadi, 2022), such as: linear programming, non-linear programming, integer programming, decision theory, queuing theory, game theory, network scheduling, information theory, Markov Process, simulation, etc. Today, operations research has a wide range of applications such as in industries, from telecommunication to health care to financial services, facilities planning, manufacturing, the construction sector, marketing, human resources, etc. Therefore, Alex Elkjær Vasegaard (Medium, 2021) tried to illustrate the complexity of operations research in terms of the related fields, subfields, and the addressed problems, although he was limited to a 2D representation as there were

many other connections between disciplines, e.g. probability theory and statistics are integral to machine learning (ML), Figure 1. Furthermore, artificial intelligence (AI), defined as machine capacity to carry out operations that ordinarily require human intellect, and ML, as a branch of AI that focuses on developing algorithms that learn from data and experience, have become essential tools for advancing operations research (Soori, 2023). AI techniques have shown great potential in improving every stage of the operations research process.

Figure 1: 2D holistic illustration of the disciplines and problems related to operations research (Medium, 2021)

In this paper are presented the research about the implementation of operations research in subjects at civil engineering and geodesy undergraduate and master academic studies in former Yugoslav republics.

2. THE IMPLEMENTATION OF OPERATIONS RESEARCH AT FACULTIES OF CIVIL ENGINEERING AND GEODESY

Operations research techniques are frequently required in engineering design, where formulating a design task as an optimization problem—without imposed economic or technical constraints—often results in multiple feasible solutions. Although these methods were initially created to address managerial and operational challenges in established systems, they are also well-suited for application in various engineering design scenarios. This is the reason why it is important to implement operations research in the engineering study programmes.

Operations research, also referred to as Management Science is the application of a scientific approach to solving difficult resource allocation, management and engineering problems in order to make better decisions. Operations research has applications in many fields, including civil and environmental engineering (Jaynes, 1957)]. There are ways to combat modeling limitations and data quality issues, but it is the responsibility of the operations research analyst to incorporate any limitations or assumptions into their analysis. Operations research tools should not be treated as a black box from which results are implemented without question, interpretation and context are vital to their successful application.

There is established EURO Working Group “Operations Research in Sustainable Development and Civil Engineering”. This idea was taken (Lownes, 2023) after a long international collaboration between researchers from several European countries (Lithuania, Germany, Poland, United Kingdom, Belgium, Denmark, Latvia,

Estonia, Czech Republic, Slovenia). The working group was created at EURO Conference XXIII in 2009, Bonn (Germany). In the 2013. in this group were more than 100 scientists from 20 countries (Lithuania, Germany, Poland, United Kingdom, Belgium, Denmark, Netherlands, Portugal, Latvia, Estonia, Czech Republic, Slovenia, Russia, Ukraine, Australia, Iran, USA, Taiwan and others), but at the early beginning research group consisted of the professors from the only Lithuanian, German and Polish academic and research centres. Marking the importance and the uniqueness of the beginning of collaboration this research group was later in articles referred to as the “scientific triangle”.

This article is written on the foundation of former research. The former research was all about civil engineering faculties and investigation of operations research subjects at the Faculties. Because of the importance of operations research in engineering studies, the research is updated with analysis of civil engineering curriculums for any changes and geodesy curriculums at the same Universities.

The implementation of operations research in civil engineering and geodesy is a need for the future, and because of that, the scope of this research is defined. The scope is to find out more about the inclusion of operations analysis and research in subjects at the Faculty of Civil Engineering and Geodesy in the former Yugoslav republics. The selection of public faculties includes one private faculty. The faculties of civil engineering and geodesy in six countries are targeted, and the curriculum of every faculty is analyzed.

In the Republic of Serbia, faculties of civil engineering in Novi Sad, Belgrade, Subotica and Niš are selected. Geodesy faculties in the Republic of Serbia are in Novi Sad, Belgrade and Subotica. There is no geodesy study programme in Niš and Novi Pazar. The one private Faculty in Belgrade is also analyzed for civil engineering studies. In Slovenia the Faculty of Civil Engineering and Geodesy in Ljubljana is analyzed. In Montenegro the Faculty of Civil Engineering in Podgorica is analyzed and geodesy study programme at the private Faculty of Applied Sciences. In Croatia the Faculty of Civil Engineering and Geodesy Faculty in Zagreb is selected. In the Republic of North Macedonia, the Faculty of Civil Engineering in Skopje, is also selected. After detailed analysis of the curriculum of undergraduate (bachelor) studies and master studies at the selected Universities the results are summarized in the Table 1.

Table 1: Subjects with implementation of operations research at the Civil Engineering and Geodesy faculties

	Year	FACULTY	CITY	STUDY PROGRAMME	SUBJECT	SCORE (ECTS)
1	5th	Faculty of Technical Sciences (Department of Civil Engineering and Geodesy)	Novi Sad	Civil engineering	The modelling of the processes in the civil engineering	3
	3rd			Geodesy	The methods of optimization	6
2	3rd	Faculty of Civil Engineering	Belgrade	Civil engineering	Informational modelling of civil engineering objects	4
	5th				Operations research	4
				Geodesy	No subject	
3	5th	UNION NIKOLA TESLA	Belgrade	Civil engineering	Operational research	5
4		Faculty of Civil Engineering and Architecture	Niš	Civil engineering	No subject	
5	2nd	Faculty of Civil Engineering	Subotica	Civil engineering	The basics of programming	7
				Geodesy	No subject	
6		Faculty of Civil Engineering	Novi Pazar	Civil engineering	No subject	
7		Faculty of Civil Engineering	Podgorica	Civil engineering	No subject	

8		Faculty of applied science	Podgorica	Geodesy	No subject	
9	5th	Faculty of Architecture, Civil Engineering and Geodesy	Banja Luka	Civil engineering	The operational research in civil engineering	4
				Geodesy	No subject	
10		Faculty of Civil Engineering	Sarajevo	Civil engineering	No subject	
				Geodesy	No subject	
11	3rd	Faculty of Civil and Geodetic Engineering	Ljubljana	Civil engineering	Project Management	4
	1st			Geodesy	Observations analysis in surveying	4
12		Faculty of Civil Engineering	Zagreb	Civil engineering	No subject	
13		Faculty of Geodesy		Geodesy	No subject	
14	3rd	Faculty of Civil Engineering	Skopje	Civil engineering	Management in civil engineering	5

At the Department of Civil Engineering and Geodesy **in Novi Sad**, there is one subject, at the 5th year of studies (1st year of master studies) called *The modelling of the processes in the civil engineering*. This subject is mandatory and carries three ECTS. Also, at the geodesy study programme there is one subject called *The methods of optimization*. This subject is mandatory and carries six ECTS.

At the Faculty of Civil Engineering **in Belgrade**, there is one subject at the 3rd year of undergraduate (bachelor) studies called *Informational modelling of civil engineering objects* and one at the 5th year called *Operations research*. These subjects are optional and carries four ECTS.

At the Faculty of Civil Engineering **UNION Nikola Tesla**, there is one subject at the 5th year of studies (1st year of master studies) called *Operational Research*. This subject is optional and carries five ECTS.

At the Faculty of Civil Engineering and Architecture **in Niš**, there is no subject in curriculum with operations research involved.

At the Faculty of Civil Engineering **in Subotica**, there is one subject at the 2nd year of undergraduate (bachelor) studies called *The basics of programming*. This subject is optional and carries seven ECTS.

At the Faculty of Civil Engineering **in Novi Pazar**, there is no subject in curriculum with operations research involved.

At the Faculty of Civil Engineering **in Podgorica**, there is no subject in curriculum with operations research involved.

At the Faculty of Architecture, Civil Engineering and Geodesy **in Banja Luka**, there is one subject at the 5th year of studies (1st year of master studies) called *The operational research in civil engineering*. This subject is optional and wears four ECTS.

At the Faculty of Civil Engineering **in Sarajevo**, there is no subject in curriculum with operations research involved.

At the Faculty of Civil and Geodetic Engineering **in Ljubljana**, there is one subject at the 3rd year of undergraduate (bachelor) studies called *Project Management* and also *Observations analysis in surveying*. The first subject is optional and carries four ECTS. The second subject is mandatory and carries four ECTS.

At the Faculty of Civil Engineering **in Zagreb**, there is no subject in curriculum with operations research involved.

At the Faculty of Civil Engineering **in Skopje**, there is one subject at the 3rd year of studies (1st year of master studies) called *Management in civil engineering*. This subject is optional and carries five ECTS.

Except at the the Department for Civil Engineering and Geodesy (Faculty of Technical Sciences, University of Novi Sad), there are no subjects about operations research at the other faculties.

After analyzing the data at the Table 1, the conclusion is that at seven faculties of civil engineering in the former Yugoslav republics, subjects connected with operations research are implemented. Five faculties of Civil Engineering do not have subjects on the implementation of operations research. Faculties that have subjects are from: Novi Sad, Belgrade, Subotica, Ljubljana, Skopje, and Banja Luka. Two geodesy Faculties

which have subjects are the Department of Civil Engineering and Geodesy in Novi Sad and the Faculty of Civil and Geodetic Engineering in Ljubljana.

Subjects are mostly optional for Civil Engineering, except for the faculty in Novi Sad. The years in which these subjects are included are the second and third in Skopje, Ljubljana, Belgrade, and Subotica. In Novi Sad, Banja Luka, Belgrade and UNION Nikola Tesla, there are subjects at the master's studies. For geodesy studies at the Department of Civil Engineering and Geodesy in Novi Sad, the subject is obligatory and it is in the third year of studies, first year at the Faculty of Civil and Geodetic Engineering in Ljubljana.

3. CONCLUSION

Operations Research, also referred to as Management Science, is the application of a scientific approach to solving difficult resource allocation, management and engineering problems in order to make better decisions.

In this work the inclusion of operations research in curriculum of civil engineering and geodesy faculties is analyzed. Six countries from region are selected: Serbia, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Croatia, Montenegro, Republic of North Macedonia and Slovenia. In that six countries fourteen faculties are selected for research. After detailed analyze of curriculums the results shows that at five faculties of Civil Engineering do not have subjects on the implementation of operations research. Faculties that have the subjects are from: Novi Sad, Belgrade, Subotica, Ljubljana, Skopje and Banja Luka. Subjects are mostly optional, except for the Faculty of Technical Sciences in Novi Sad. Two geodesy Faculties which have subjects are the Department of Civil Engineering and Geodesy in Novi Sad and the Faculty of Civil and Geodetic Engineering in Ljubljana.

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